

A STUDY ON PREVALENCE OF OVERWEIGHT AND OBESITY AMONG UNDERGRADUATE MARITIME CADETS IN INDIA

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Abstract:

Background

In today's 'Obesogenic' modern environment, overweight and obesity are well-recognised causes of not only the physical inability among seafarers but also a safety issue on board ships. Overweight and obesity develop due to multifactorial causes such as environment, socio economic status, genetics, metabolism, behavior or life style habits, and more. The prevalence of overweight and obesity has been shown to increase the likelihood of developing metabolic diseases such as cardiovascular diseases, diabetes mellitus, stroke, infertility, liver disorders, respiratory ailments and certain cancers. Most of the causes of overweight and obesity are preventable.

Methods

The present study included a random sample of 102 undergraduate students enrolled for training at Indian maritime university in Mumbai, India. Multiple variables such as demographic profile, family history of medical ailments, exercise details, fatty food consumption, sleep pattern, personal habits (smoking & alcohol consumption), personal medical ailments and anthropometry measurements were recorded for analysis.

Results

All the respondents in the study group were unmarried males in the age group 19 to 23 years and pursuing undergraduate maritime course at the university. While only 5 % of the respondents reported to have medical ailments such as Hypertension, allergies, asthma etc., a significant number of 17.6 % reported family history of medical ailments such as diabetes, hypertension, heart ailments and obesity. With respect to lifestyle habits, 72.4 % of the individuals consume fried and oily food frequently, 27.5 % of respondents exercise less frequently. In this study we have evaluated the prevalence of overweight and obesity by calculating the BMI of the respondents. The mean BMI of the study group was 22.49 ± 2.10 kg/m², Mean WHR was 0.93 ± 0.04 . The respondents were classified as per the recommended BMI cut off points for Asians and it was found that only 56.86% were having normal BMI, 32.35 % were overweight and 7.84% were obese. Multiple regression analysis with BMI as the dependent variable showed exercise habit, waist circumference and hip circumference to be the significant influencing determinants ($R^2=0.418$, $p=0.000$). Individuals who exercise less frequently showed a greater tendency to being overweight and obese when compared with other respondents in the study group.

Conclusion

Our study showed that a significant number (over 40 %) of undergraduate cadets were classified (as per the Asian target cut-off) as overweight or obese even at such a young age. As most of the causative factors of overweight and obesity are modifiable, a positive change in them will bring about healthy life especially in the younger population. In order to keep the seafarers community healthy, awareness campaigns of the phenomenon and the danger of the health ill effects should be promoted. Special initiatives to promote physical exercise sessions and monitoring of junk food consumption should be implemented at the training level itself to keep the young seafarers motivated for a healthy lifestyle.

Keywords

Seafarers' Health; Overweight; Obesity; BMI; Exercise.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's 'Obesogenic' modern environment, overweight and obesity are well-recognised causes of not only the physical inability among seafarers but also a safety issue on board ships.

Overweight and obesity are both, ranges of weight that are greater than what is generally considered healthy for a given height. Overweight and obesity develop when the energy intake from food consumption is greater than the energy expenditure through the body's metabolism. The health risks of overweight and obesity were worse than smoking, drinking or poverty and is known to increase the likelihood of Non-Communicable Diseases [NCDs] like cardiovascular diseases, diabetes mellitus, stroke, infertility, liver disorders, respiratory ailments and certain cancers¹. Overweight and obesity develop due to multifactorial causes such as environment, socio economic status, genetics, metabolism, behaviour or life style habits, and more. Most of the causes of overweight and obesity are preventable. It is important to prevent acquired diseases and post pone inherited diseases to increase the quality of life.

Body Mass Index (BMI) is considered the most useful and simple measure of overweight and obesity². However, the BMI value should be interpreted with caution because it is not a direct measure of adiposity (amount of body fat) of an individual. The BMI is calculated by dividing the person's weight in kilograms with the square of their height in meters (kg/m²). The WHO standard for overweight and obesity among adults is Underweight- Less than 18.5kg/m², Normal weight - 18.5–24.9kg/m², Overweight (or pre-obese) - 25–29.9kg/m², Obesity (class I)- 30–34.9kg/m², Moderate Obesity (class II) - 35–39.9kg/m² and Severe Obesity (class III) - 40kg/m² or more. Keeping in view the genetic and ethnic predispositions and variability, the WHO expert consultation group recommended 23kg/m² for increased risk and 27.5kg/m² for high risk as trigger points for public health action for adults of Asian origin^{3,4}. Waist circumference (WC) and Waist-Hip Ratio (WHR) are other methods to measure body fat distribution or 'Central obesity'. An individual is at moderate risk if his Waist circumference ≥ 94 cm (males) and ≥ 80 cm (females); and at greatly increased risk if WC is ≥ 102 cm (males) and ≥ 88 cm (females). A raised WHR is commonly taken to be ≥ 1.0 in men, and ≥ 0.85 in women in at risk individuals.

1.1 Materials and Methods

This study was cross sectional in nature, using a random sample of students enrolled for pre-sea training during May 2018 at Indian Maritime University, Mumbai, India. All the students were informed of the purpose and invited to participate voluntarily. No exclusion criteria were applied as all the volunteers belonged to the same group of pre-sea trainees. The participants were asked to fill a structured questionnaire. The

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questionnaire required details of individual’s age, gender, educational background, primary place of work, family history of medical ailments, exercise details, fatty food consumption, sleep, personal habits (smoking & alcohol consumption), personal medical history and anthropometry measurements. The participants were asked to record the anthropometry measurements (height, weight, waist circumference and hip circumference) at the university medical centre for accuracy. The measurements were taken as per the standard guidelines.

1.1 To determine height

Participants were asked to remove their shoes, heavy outer garments, and hair ornaments. The participant was asked to stand with his/her back to the height rule. The back of the head, back, buttocks, calves and heels were in contact with the stadiometer, with the feet together. The measurement was noted to the nearest 0.1 cm.

1.2 To determine weight

The Calibrated weighing scale was placed on a hard-floor surface. Participants were asked to wear light clothing, remove their shoes and empty their pockets. The measurement was noted to the nearest 0.1kg.

1.3 To determine waist and hip measurement

A standard measuring tape was used to measure the circumference of the participant’s hip at the widest part of the buttocks and waist at the smaller circumference of the natural waist. The measurement was noted to the nearest 0.1 cm.

The data was analysed using statistical programme for social studies (SPSS Version 16). Frequencies, descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and linear regression analysis tests were conducted.

2. RESULTS

In this study, the valid data from 102 individuals were analysed. Table 1, summarizes the demographic and anthropometric characteristics of the individuals. All the 102 respondents were unmarried males in the age group 19 years to 23 years, pursuing their undergraduate maritime course at the university.

BODY MASS INDEX in kg/m ²	15.06	27.08	22.49	2.10
WAIST TO HIP RATIO	0.73	1.07	0.93	0.04
WAIST TO HEIGHT RATIO	0.40	0.60	0.47	0.03

85.3 % of the respondents reported their primary place of work as ship deck while for 5.9 % the workplace was ship bridge and the rest 8.8 % all other work areas in the ship. While 82.4 % of the individuals reported no family history of medical ailments, a significant number of 17.6 % reported family history of medical ailments such as diabetes, hypertension, heart ailments and obesity (figure 1).

Figure 1. Percentage of respondents with family history of medical ailments (N=102)

With regard to the personal health of the individuals, most of them (95.1%) do not have any significant medical history. Very few individuals had reported history of Asthma (1 %), Hypertension (1 %), allergies (2 %) and other ailments like skin diseases etc. (1 %). None of the respondents reported personal habits of either smoking or consuming alcohol.

Figure 2 shows the frequency of fried and oily food consumption by the respondents. 72.4 % of the individuals consume fried and oily food frequently while 27.5 % either do not consume or take oily food very rarely.

Figure 2. Frequency of Fried / Oily food consumption by the respondents (N=102)

97% of the respondents slept comfortably and 3% reported mostly disturbed sleep. With respect to quality of sleep, most

Table 1: Demographic and Anthropometric characteristics (N=102)

Parameters	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
AGE in years	19	23	20.91	0.86
HEIGHT in cm	160	190	173.86	5.70
WEIGHT in cm	51	93	68.05	7.76
WAIST CIRCUMFERENCE in cm	71	105	81.68	5.47
HIP CIRCUMFERENCE in cm	74	115	87.52	6.92

individuals attributed the disturbance in quality of sleep to be due to work (39.2 %), surrounding environment (26.5 %), living condition (12.7 %), anxiety (6.9 %). 14.7 % individuals could not attribute any specific reason to the disturbance in sleep (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Attributes for disturbance in quality of sleep of respondents (N=102)

72.6% of the respondents reported exercising regularly while the rest of them were exercising only occasionally. (figure 4).

Figure 4. Regularity of exercise routine among respondents (N=102)

Classification of the respondents based on their BMI (figure 5) shows that as per the WHO classification 89.22% of the respondents were having normal BMI and 7.84% of them were overweight and none were obese. Whereas when the respondents were classified as per the recommended cut off points for Asians it was found that only 56.86% were having normal BMI, 32.35 % were overweight and 7.84% were obese.

Figure 5. Classification of respondents (N=102) based on Body Mass Index

The respondents were classified into 4 groups (Table 2) as per the WHO recommended Asian cutoff points for BMI, 3 respondents fell in Group 1 (underweight (BMI <18.5)), 58 were in Group 2 (Normal BMI (BMI 18.5 to 22.99)), 33 were classified as Group 3 (overweight (BMI 23 to 24.99)) and 8 were in group 4 (obese (BMI ≥ 25)).

Age of respondents in years	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
	Underweight BMI < 18.5	Normal BMI 18.5 to 22.99	Overweight BMI 23 to 24.99	Obesity BMI ≥ 25
19	0	1	0	0
20	1	21	10	3
21	0	23	15	4
22	1	11	7	1
23	1	2	1	0
Total Respondents	3	58	33	8

Table 2: Group classification of respondents based on BMI - WHO Asian cutoff (N=102)

On comparison of the four groups, it was found that as the BMI increases, there is a decrease in exercise time of the respondents, increase in their Waist and hip circumferences, increase in weight, and increase in waist to height ratio. Whereas, no appreciable changes in age, height and WHR was found with increase in BMI of the respondent (Table 3)

Table 3: Comparison of anthropometric measurements of BMI Groups (N=102)

Parameters	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
	Underweight BMI < 18.5	Normal BMI 18.5 to 22.99	Overweight BMI 23 to 24.99	Obesity BMI ≥ 25
Number of Respondents	3	58	33	8
Age in years	21.67 ± 1.53	20.86 ± 0.87	20.97 ± 0.81	20.75 ± 0.71
Exercise time in minutes /day	86.67 ± 35.12	52.93 ± 24.08	50.15 ± 24.92	38.75 ± 13.30

Height in cm	175.00 ± 8.54	174.28 ± 5.53	172.7 ± 5.27	175.25 ± 7.78
Weight in cm	52.33 ± 2.31	65.02 ± 5.63	71.70 ± 5.18	80.88 ± 7.26
Waist circumference in cm	73.59 ± 2.44	79.95 ± 3.45	83.05 ± 4.85	91.53 ± 7.29
Hip circumference in cm	79.40 ± 3.42	85.15 ± 4.51	89.87 ± 7.05	98.01 ± 8.24
Body mass index (BMI in kg/m ²)	17.17 ± 1.83	21.38 ± 1.17	24.01 ± 0.56	26.29 ± 0.71
Waist to hip ratio (WHR)	0.93 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.03	0.93 ± 0.05	0.93 ± 0.02
Waist to height ratio (W/Ht-R)	0.42 ± 0.01	0.46 ± 0.02	0.48 ± 0.03	0.52 ± 0.03

A multivariate linear regression model was proposed in which BMI was proposed to be a dependent variable on independent variables – age, Exercise time, Hip circumference and Waist circumference respectively. The model showed a significant positive influence of Waist circumference and Hip circumference on BMI, whereas significant negative influence of Exercise time was observed on BMI. Age is not a significant variable at 5 % level of confidence. Of the significantly influencing independent variables, Hip circumference has the highest magnitude of influence followed by Waist circumference and Exercise time. The model has a reasonable explanatory power ($r^2=0.418$), thus inferring that variations in independent variables correlated with variations in dependent variables to an estimated precision of 41.8%. (Table 4).

Table 4: Multivariate analysis – linear regression (n=102)
Dependent Variable – BMI

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	9.080	4.617		1.967	0.052
Hip Circumference	0.096	0.043	0.316	2.218	0.029
Waist Circumference	0.119	0.055	0.309	2.145	0.034
Exercise Time	-0.016	0.007	-0.188	-2.344	0.021
Age	-0.186	0.191	-0.076	-0.973	0.333

$R^2=0.418$, $F = 17.385$, $Sig. 0.000$ [$p < 0.050$ is significant]

3. DISCUSSION

The respondents in the present study were all pursuing an undergraduate course at Indian Maritime University in Navi-Mumbai campus. Typically, the students join the course immediately after completing their school studies and through a competitive examination. Hence it is imperative that the respondents of the study are young aged (19 to 23 years) and possess good knowledge. As per the Indian census report 2011, half of the population is under the age of 25 years and Two-thirds

are less than 35 years. The study group represents the dominant population group in India. Most of the respondents (82.4 %) typically do not have any medical ailment. At this young age most of the individuals do not exhibit any medical ailments. It is generally known that disability and mortality are age-related. It is a natural phenomenon that, the older individuals grow, the more likely they are predisposed to various health conditions. Most medical ailments are caused by a combination of genetic, lifestyle and environmental factors. The importance of any particular factor varies from person to person. Family history of health risks or ailments is an important tool for understanding health risks and preventing some chronic diseases (e.g., hypertension, heart disease, diabetes and cancer) in individuals⁵. While majority of respondents reported no family history of medical ailments, 17.6% reported family history of Diabetes Mellitus, hypertension, heart ailment or obesity. This group of individuals have a potential risk and will benefit by regular screening and preventive measures.

Lifestyle and behavior choices are important determinants in influencing the health status of an individual. Life style health risk determinants primarily include smoking habit, alcohol consumption, unhealthy diet, lack of physical activity and, sleep deprivation. These determinants have a cumulative effect on the burden of disease in the individual. In the present study, none of the respondents reported smoking habit or alcohol consumption, a good sign of health awareness among the group. 14.7 % respondents consume fried /oily food very frequently (every day or 4-5 times a week). This kind of dietary habit results in excess consumption of calories, saturated fats, Trans-Fatty Acids (TFAs), simple sugars, salt and low intake of fibre, leading to greater risk of developing non communicable diseases. Frequent snacking on energy-dense fast foods, high consumption of packaged foods and easy availability of convenience foods in place of traditional homemade foods has resulted increased incidence of NCD's among young individuals^{6,7}. Majority of the respondents reported regularity in exercising. About 27.5 % of the individuals exercised infrequently. Moderate physical activity is part of the student life and balances infrequent exercising. Physical activity is a key determinant of energy balance and weight control for the body. Low levels of physical inactivity cause weight gain and increase in BMI of an individual leading to overweight and obesity. Regular physical activity will improve the overall health and fitness of the individual, and reduce the risk for chronic ailments⁸. Most of the respondents did not report any sleep deprivation, but attributed the disturbance in quality of sleep to be mainly due to work pressures, environment and living conditions⁹. Long work schedules and improper time management and stress lead to change in the sleep pattern and play a vital role in compounding the effect of health risks. Shift duties in particular causes a permanent conflict in biological clock of human body and results in risk of ill health in the individual.

Body Mass Index (BMI) was used as the main measure of determining the incidence of overweight and obesity among the respondents. Respondents were classified into underweight, normal and overweight/obesity based on both the WHO global standards as well as the WHO Asian Indian Cut-off standards for comparison. When the WHO global standards are applied, majority (89.22 %) of the respondents have normal BMI but a

significant (7.84 %) number of them are overweight/obese. While with the WHO Asian Indian standards, it is observed that 32.35% of the respondents belonged to overweight category with BMI ≥ 23 kg/m² and 7.84 % of them fall under obese category with BMI ≥ 25 kg/m². This is an alarming trend considering the fact that the mean age of this young student cohort is only 20.91 \pm 0.86 years and about 40% of these respondents are at risk of developing NCD's. The present study shows that near about half the individuals are at risk of ill health in the near future even without considering the other health risk determinants like age, genetic predisposition and life style factors. A combined effect of more than one of the health risk determinants would make the individuals more vulnerable to burden of disease. On comparison of the four BMI groups, classified based on the WHO Asian Indian Cut-off standards, showed a corresponding increase in the other anthropometric measurements with increasing BMI reiterating the presence of the 'obesogenic' group in this young cohort. Multivariate analysis showed that Hip circumference, waist circumference and time spent on exercise were significant influencers of BMI of the individual. The propensity of the individual to be overweight or obese is dependent on his exercise regularity.

In the present study group comprising of young and educated respondents a significant number of them are vulnerable to ill health due to presence of family history of ailments, unhealthy dietary habits and lack of exercise proportionate to the age of the individual. Health promotion and education in the young individuals will inculcate awareness among them and will help them avoid health risks and stay fit to cope up with the rigor of seafaring.

4. CONCLUSION

The present study showed that the young undergraduate maritime cadets seemed healthy as do not report any medical ailments but a significant number of them were found to have health risk attributes like unhealthy diet and lack of quality exercise time making them vulnerable to disease state. Also, as per the WHO Asian Indian Cut-off standards significant number of them fall in the category of overweight or obesity even at such a young age. As most of the causative factors of overweight and obesity are lifestyle and behavioural choice related like physical activity, healthy diet, work sleep pattern and personal habits, they are all modifiable and a positive change in them will bring about healthy life especially in the younger population. As the individual ages, non-modifiable variables such as age and genetic predisposition also begin to influence and the combined impact of all the health risk variables will lead to disease burden by the time he turns middle aged and will be further burdened with occupational stress. As age advances, personal, family, occupational and, social responsibilities add up. These coupled with health risk determinants can lead to physical, mental and social ill health of an individual. In order to keep the seafarers community healthy, awareness campaigns of the phenomenon and the danger of the health ill effects should be promoted. Special initiatives to promote physical exercise sessions and monitoring of junk food consumption should be implemented at the training level itself to keep the young seafarers motivated for a healthy lifestyle.

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